

RESULTS OF THE SCORE (SUSTAINABLE CONSERVATION AND RESTORATION OF BUILT CULTURAL HERITAGE) PROJECT

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1. Introduction

SCORE Project (Sustainable CONservation and REStoration of built cultural heritage) is a MSCA RISE project started on January 2021 that will finish in October 2025. The SCORE project takes place in a favourable global context and brings together an intersectoral, international and multidisciplinary group including a wide range of actors – materials scientists, biologists and civil engineering researchers, archaeologists, art historians, Life Cycle Assessment specialists, climatologists, practitioners, consulting companies, training organisations, decision-makers and non-governmental organisations – in order to strengthen collaborative research and innovation in eco-friendly conservation, restoration, and rehabilitation.

The SCORE project has three research and innovation objectives:

1. The development of “green” innovations: materials and methods for the conservation of ancient buildings based on a circular economy philosophy.
2. Two-way assessment of impacts of the environment on materials and of materials on the environment: Climate conditions and atmosphere composition determine built cultural heritage (BCH) materials’ behaviour and, at the same time, the BCH conservation process (products and techniques) impacts greenhouse gases emissions and then climate change.
3. Training and knowledge transfer on both innovative and traditional materials and methods with a low environmental impact.

With SCORE, new collaborations between researchers, private companies, non-governmental organisations and stakeholders have been established. The research and innovation actions are based on expertise exchange and knowledge sharing in the conservation, restoration and rehabilitation of two kinds of BCH in two geographical and climatic areas: vernacular BCH in Europe and archaeological sites (850-1200 CE) in Mexico. These two kinds of built cultural heritage

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have been chosen because 1) vernacular BCH is much less protected than monuments by national and international legislation and conventions, therefore more vulnerable; 2) Mexico has around 25,000 pre-Hispanic archaeological sites and the amount of archaeological built cultural heritage makes it difficult to protect and needs critical efforts and budgets.

2. Methodology

The SCORE project is organised in 5 work packages represented in Figure 1.

3. Main results

Main published results can be consulted in <https://zenodo.org/communities/score/>

3.1 Work package 2: studies and characterization of buildings and materials

A complete description of each case study (6 in Europe and 2 in Mexico) has been done, including geopolitics environment, building typology, employed materials, etc. The employed materials in several sites have been characterised: composition, microstructure, physical properties.

Figure 1: Working methodology of the SCORE project. WP1 corresponds to the project management and coordination.

3.2 Work package 3: Design of Eco-efficient conservation materials

Two main types of materials have been proposed, 1) lime restoration mortars and renders; 2) nanoparticles treatments against soiling and biological colonisation. All the materials have been characterised in the laboratory and their durability tested in the laboratory and *in situ*. The exposition tests *in situ* have been done in real cases (buildings) and in racks exposed in the case study sites.

3.3 Work package 4: Simulation and modelling

This work page includes *severa et pas aux normes!* aspects: 1) development of new estimators of the weathering process (dose response functions or weather thresholds); 2) Climate models' realisation in the case study and application of several dose response functions in order to compare the future weathering of the case studies; 3) estimation of the environmental impacts of lime mortars life and of restoration works in Chichen Itza (Mexico).

3.4 Work package 5: Training & knowledge-sharing

Many different activities have been accomplished, including the organisation of the STONE 2025 conference and its summer school. Other activities concern a summer school, Envimat 2022; several curricula courses in partners universities; invited conferences and intensive courses, student reports about valorisation of built cultural heritage, etc.

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